

THE DIFFERENCE IN SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE BETWEEN ARMS AND LOWER LIMBS IS THE NOVEL RISK MARKER FOR DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN PATIENTS OF TYPE II DIABETES

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE:

To find the diagnostic accuracy of inter-arms and inter-leg systolic blood pressure (SBP) difference in detection of diabetic nephropathy in patients of type II diabetes taking urinary protein levels as gold standard

Study Design: Cross-sectional study

Study place and period: The study was done at department of Medicine, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from 01 February 2025 till 30 June 2025

Methodology: After fulfilling the inclusion criteria, a total of 300 patients were recruited. The SBP difference in right and left sides was calculated as the absolute value (right-left) for both upper and lower limbs in each patient. A difference of ≥ 10 mmHg between both arms and legs was considered indicative of diabetic nephropathy. A 24-hour urine sample was collected and sent to the hospital laboratory. Patients were classified as positive or negative for diabetic nephropathy.

Results: In this study using urine protein level as the gold standard, the inter-arm SBP difference exhibited 43.9% sensitivity, 97.2% specificity and 64.5% diagnostic accuracy to detect the diabetic nephropathy. Similarly, the inter-leg SBP exhibited 77.5% sensitivity, 80.9% specificity 79.3% diagnostic accuracy to detect the diabetic nephropathy in diabetic patients.

Conclusion: Inter-leg SBP difference demonstrated greater diagnostic accuracy and more reliable performance in detecting diabetic nephropathy when urine protein level was considered the gold standard.

INTRODUCTION

Type II diabetes mellitus is the major public health burden and a rising healthcare concern all around the world. The number of people with this form of diabetes are increasing day by day in low- and middle-income regions of the world in high-income areas.¹ Based on meta-analysis, composed of 49,418 diabetic individuals, prevalence of diabetes in Pakistan was calculated to be 14.62% and of pre-diabetes was 11.43%.²

Although the number of people with diabetes mellitus is rising, it is still unclear how common

diabetic nephropathy is in diabetic patients.³ Vascular complications include coronary heart disease, stroke, diabetic nephropathy, and end-stage renal disease have developed as a result of diabetes's rising incidence.⁴ Diabetic nephropathy was seen in 23.3% of type II diabetic individuals in Pakistan.⁵ A higher risk of peripheral artery disease, cardiovascular disease, and death has been associated with an elevated inter-arm blood pressure differential (IABPD) of $\lesssim 10$ mmHg.⁶⁻⁸ IABPD may be a strong predictor of cardiovascular risks and

potentially peripheral artery disease, according to recent research. Nevertheless, nothing is known about the relationship between IABPD and peripheral artery disease in diabetic patients.⁹

In routine, 24-h urinary samples are taken to diagnose the diabetic nephropathy, which is usually hard to collect and usually associated with risk contamination. Routine, blood pressure assessment can be helpful in predicting the nephropathy and can help to early diagnose and manage the diabetic nephropathy. There is very little information available in literature, regarding the accuracy of difference in blood pressure assessment for prediction of nephropathy and local evidence is not available. Therefore, we want to conduct this study to get updated results and implement findings in local setting and updated our knowledge and practice. So, this study aimed to find the diagnostic accuracy of inter-arms & inter-leg SBP difference in the detection of diabetic nephropathy among diabetic patients taking urinary protein levels as gold standard.

METHODOLOGY

After taking approval from ethical review committee, this cross-sectional study was done out at department of Medicine, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from 01 February 2025 till 30 June 2025. Total sample size for this study was 300 cases. The sample size was calculated by using WHO sample size calculator taking prevalence of diabetic nephropathy i.e. 23.3%, 5 sensitivity of difference in leg blood pressure i.e. 68.8% with 11% margin of error and specificity of difference in leg blood pressure i.e. 62.4% with 6.5% margin of error¹⁰. All the individuals were included by applying non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion: Patients having age range between 35 to 75 years of both gender, having diabetes HbA1c > 6.5% for >1 year but < 5 years, having BMI > 24 kg/m² and have renal function (serum Creatinine < 2.0mg/dl) were fall in inclusion criteria.

Exclusion: Patients with malignancy, smoking (>5 pack years), alcoholism (>20 ml/day), on lipid lowering drugs, diabetic peripheral nephropathy, vasculopathy were fall in exclusion criteria.

All the included patients were recruited from OPD after taking written consent. Demographics were taken. The sphygmomanometer, which monitors arm and ankle SBP was applied for both sides. Three values were taken and their average value was calculated. The patient was allowed to lie down for a minimum of five minutes before the blood pressure was measured. Three readings were averaged to arrive at the final figure. The absolute difference between the arms and lower limbs was determined and reported for each individual's SBP discrepancies. The absolute value of right-left was used to compute the blood pressure difference. If there was ≥ 10 mmHg difference in blood pressure of both arms and both legs, then diabetic nephropathy was labeled. Meanwhile, 24-h urine sample was taken and sent to the pathology laboratory to assess the urinary protein level and urine albumin level. Findings were obtained and diabetic nephropathy was labeled as positive or negative for. On 24-h urinary protein, was labelled as positive if there was proteinuria ≥ 300 mg/dl. All this information was recorded on proforma.

All the data was analyzed on SPSS v.25. 2x2 table was developed to calculate the sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values and diagnostic accuracy of difference in arm or legs SBP level.

RESULTS:

In this study, the mean age of individuals was 55.46 ± 12.40 years, and mean BMI was 31.27 ± 4.56 kg/m². Of the participants, 161 (53.7%) were male candidates and 139 (46.3%) were female candidates. Regarding occupation, the majority were housewives, accounting for 110 (36.7%) patients. An active lifestyle was reported in 37 (12.3%) patients, whereas 263 (87.7%) had a sedentary lifestyle. Additionally, 131 (43.7%) participants belonged to the middle socioeconomic class. According to the study findings, 135 (45%) patients were hypertensive, 155 (51.7%) were diabetic, and a family history of diabetes mellitus was noted in 49 (16.3%) cases. The mean period of diabetes diagnosis was 2.89 ± 1.42 years. **Table-I**

The mean inter-arm SBP difference was 0.36 ± 26.20 mmHg, while the mean inter-leg SBP

difference was 1.32 ± 27.34 mmHg. The average 24-hour urinary protein level was 355.82 ± 271.03 mg. Diabetic nephropathy was detected in 128 (42.7%) patients in the upper limbs and in 138 (46%) patients in the lower limbs, whereas urinary involvement due to diabetic nephropathy was observed in 46% of patients.

Table-II

According to this study the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy of inter-am SBP difference for detection of diabetic nephropathy was 43.9%, 97.2%, 96.1%, 52.3% and 64.5% respectively taking

urine protein level as gold standard. Similarly the sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy of inter-leg SBP difference for detection of diabetic nephropathy was 77.5%, 80.9%, 77.5%, 80.9% & 79.3% respectively taking urine protein level as gold standard. **Table-III**

Table 4 showed the validity of inter-arm difference of SBP and inter-leg difference of BSP for detection of diabetic retinopathy taking urine protein level as gold standard stratified by age, gender, hypertension, DM, life style and BMI of the patients. **Table-IV**

Table-I: Demographics and clinical history of enrolled patients (n = 300)

Parameters	F (%)	
Age (years)	55.46 ± 12.40	
Gender	Males	161 (53.7%)
	Females	139 (46.3%)
Occupation	Job	81 (27.0%)
	Business	67 (22.3%)
	Housewife	110 (36.7%)
	Retired	42 (14.0%)
Life Style	Active	37 (12.3%)
	Sedentary	263 (87.7%)
Socioeconomic status	Low class	106 (35.3%)
	Middle class	131 (43.7%)
	High class	63 (21.0%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	31.27 ± 4.56	
BMI Groups	Overweight	118 (39.3%)
	Obese	100 (33.3%)
	Morbidly obese	82 (27.3%)
Hypertension	135 (45.0%)	
Diabetes Mellitus	155 (51.7%)	
Family history of diabetes	49 (16.3%)	
Duration of diabetes	2.89 ± 1.42	

Table-II: Descriptive statistics of clinical and outcome parameters of the patients

	Frequency
Blood pressure left arm	147.06 ± 29.58
Blood pressure right arm	147.42 ± 27.91
Difference of blood pressure in arm	0.36 ± 26.20
Blood pressure left leg	150.58 ± 29.20
Blood pressure right leg	149.26 ± 28.09
Difference of blood pressure among legs	1.32 ± 27.34
24 Hour Urine Protein	355.82 ± 271.03

Table-III: Validity of blood pressure difference of arm and leg for detection of diabetic nephropathy taking urine protein level as gold standard

Diabetic Nephropathy		Urine Protein			Total	
		Positive	Negative			
Inter-arm	Positive	123	5		128	
	Negative	15	157		172	
Total		138	162		300	
Inter-arm Leg	Positive	107	31		138	
	Negative	31	131		162	
Total		138	162		300	
		Urine Protein (Gold Standard)				
		Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Diagnostic Accuracy
Inter-arms		43.9%	97.2%	96.1%	52.3%	64.5%
Inter-legs		77.5%	80.9%	77.5%	80.9%	79.3%

Table-IV: Validity of inter-arm difference blood pressure and inter leg difference blood pressure for detection of diabetic retinopathy taking urine protein level as gold standard stratified for effect modifiers

Arm difference/leg difference		Urine Protein (Gold Standard)				
		Sensitivity (arm/leg)	Specificity (arm/leg)	PPV (arm/leg)	NPV (arm/leg)	Diagnostic Accuracy (arm/leg)
Age Groups	≤50	89.3/71.4	96.9/81.2	96.1/76.9	91.2/76.5	93.3/76.7
	>50	89.2/81.7	89.3/80.6	96.0/77.9	73.5/84	89.1/81.1
Gender	Male	88.2/75	95.7/83.9	93.7/77.3	91.7/82.1	92.5/80.1
	Female	90/80	98.5/76.8	98.4/77.8	90.6/79.1	94.2/78.4
Hypertension	Yes	88.7/72.5	95.9/87.7	94.8/83.3	90.9/79.01	92.6/80.7
DM	Yes	91.7/79.2	98.7/82	98.9/81.3	90.6/80	94.8/80.6
Life Style	Active	88.2/82.3	95/85	93.7/82.3	90.5/85	91.9/83.7
	Sedentary	89.3/76.8	97.2/80.3	96.4/76.9	91.4/80.3	93.5/78.7
BMI	Overweight	94.5/78.2	96.8/74.6	96.3/72.9	95.3/79.6	95.7/76.3
	Obese	84/72	98/84	97.7/81.8	85.9/75	91/78
	Morbidly obese	87.9/84.8	95.9/85.7	93.5/80	92.1/89.4	92.7/85.4

DISCUSSION:

In this study using urine protein level as the gold standard, the inter-arm SBP difference demonstrated a sensitivity of 43.9%, specificity of 97.2%, PPV of 96.1%, NPV of 52.3%, and an overall diagnostic accuracy of 64.5% for the detection of diabetic nephropathy. Similarly, the inter-leg blood pressure difference showed a sensitivity of 77.5%, specificity of 80.9%, PPV of 77.5%, NPV of 80.9%, and a diagnostic accuracy of 79.3% in detecting diabetic nephropathy, when urine protein level was considered the gold standard.

According to clinical practice recommendations, SBP must be assessed for both arms in diabetic patients. If the results

differ, the side with the high value must be used for diagnosis. Typically, the right side has high SBP than left side. This can be explained by the fact that the left subclavian artery starts in the aorta and makes an acute angle along its course, which causes turbulence and lowers blood flow.¹¹⁻¹³ According to recent research, vascular disease and death are linked to differences in SBP between both arms.¹⁴ Even for inter-arm SBP differences of ≤ 5 mmHg, without SBP interaction, a correlation between the occurrence of diabetic retinopathy and the inter-arm SBP difference was seen. In diabetic patients diabetes, the systolic inter-arm SBP

difference should be regarded as a proxy for vascular complications.¹⁵

To detect diabetic nephropathy in diabetic individuals, the sensitivity & specificity of difference between both arms were 75% & 59.3%, respectively. While the corresponding values for both legs were 68.8% and 62.4%.¹⁰ According to a study by Bande et al., the inter-arm variation in SBP may be a risk indicator for kidney impairment in diabetes mellitus.¹⁶ In their study, Lee et al. showed that, even in cases where the inter-arm SBP difference was less than 5 mmHg and there was no interaction with the SBP, there was a correlation between the occurrence of diabetic retinopathy and the inter-arm SBP difference. In patients with type II diabetes, the inter-arm SBP difference should be regarded as a proxy for vascular complications.¹⁷

According to the findings of another study, the correlation between ankle brachial index (ABI) and inter-arm SBP differences provides important information about detecting peripheral artery disease in diabetic individuals.¹⁸ Another study by Miyashima et al., conducted a similar study on 1,316 diabetic individuals and observed that there was high difference in inter-arms SBP ($P = 0.01$) and a higher prevalence of difference of ≥ 10 mmHg between both arms SBP (8.4% vs. 5.4%, $P < 0.05$) when compared to 1,264 nondiabetic controls. However, once possible confounders were taken into account, the difference was no longer significant.¹⁹

According to Lin et al., a higher incidence of apparent peripheral nephropathy was linked to a rise in the ILSBPD (≥ 15 mmHg) in persons with diabetes in the United States. Even after controlling for covariates, the author demonstrated that the ILSBPD ≥ 15 mmHg group had a substantially higher incidence of evident peripheral nephropathy (OR 1.79, 95% CI 1.11–2.91, $P = 0.018$).²⁰

CONCLUSION:

Thus inter-leg blood pressure difference demonstrated greater diagnostic accuracy and more reliable performance in detecting diabetic nephropathy. Therefore, routine assessment of blood pressure can be helpful in predicting the nephropathy and can help to early diagnose

and manage the diabetic nephropathy. Now in future, we will implement findings in local setting and make it regular practice.

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